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28 New labelled PET analogues enable the functional screening and characterization of
29 PET-degrading enzymes

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35 **and characterization of PET-degrading enzymes**

36

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71 **Figure S1.** Methodological approach in synthesis of **PET[B]-COOH** and **PET[C/D]-**
 72 **COOH** precursors: A) 2- ethoxyethanol, KOH, toluene, 120 °C, 4 h; B) DCC/DMAP,
 73 CH₂Cl₂, r.t., 12 h; C) H₂ (balloon), Pd/C, 1,4- dioxane, r.t., 6 h.

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75 Experimental procedures

76 **4-((2-ethoxyethoxy)carbonyl)benzoic acid (4):** Potassium hydroxide (0.36 g; 6.4
 77 mmol; 1 eq) was dissolved in 2- ethoxyethanol (0.6 mL; 6.4 mmol; 1 eq) with stirring
 78 and gentle heating. Then, solution of *bis*(2-ethoxyethyl)terephthalate **1** (Chase ,1963;
 79 Djapovic et al., 2021) (2.00 g; 6.4 mmol; 1 eq) and toluene (30.0 mL) was added, and
 80 reaction mixture was heated at 120 °C for 4h. After cooling to room temperature, the
 81 reaction mixture was filtered, and the remaining filter cake of the ionic salt was washed
 82 with EtOAc. After the filter cake was well dried, it was dispersed in water (25.0 mL),
 83 and then the aqueous solution was washed with EtOAc (3 x 15.0 mL). The aqueous
 84 solution was acidified with HCl (conc.) to pH = 2 and then the acid was extracted from
 85 the aqueous layer with EtOAc. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄,
 86 the solvent was evaporated using a vacuum evaporator. 0.71 g (**47%**) of the acid
 87 **PET[B]-COOH** was obtained in the form of a white, crystalline substance (mp 88-90
 88 °C). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 8.15 – 8.09 (m, 4H), 4.52 (m, 2H), 3.81 (m, 2H),
 89 3.62 (q, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H), 1.25 (t, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C
 90 170.4, 165.9, 134.8, 133.3, 130.2, 129.9, 68.5, 66.9, 64.7, 15.2. IR (ATR) ν_{max}: 3063,
 91 2977, 2863, 2670, 2553, 1712, 1688, 1575, 1510, 1428, 1355, 1276, 1130, 1112, 731.
 92 HRMS (ESI): m/z [M+Na]⁺ calculated for C₁₂H₁₄O₅: 261.0733; found: 261.0734.

93 **Benzyl (2-((4-(methoxycarbonyl)benzoyl)oxy)ethyl) terephthalate (5):** A solution
94 of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) (576.0 mg; 2.79 mmol; 1.1 eq) in dichloromethane
95 (6 mL) was added dropwise to a cold (0 °C) suspension of monobenzyl terephthalate **4**
96 (651 mg; 2.54 mmol; 1 eq), PET monomer **3** (Djapovic et al., 2021) (570 mg; 2.54
97 mmol; 1.0 eq), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (155 mg; 1.27 mmol; 0.5 eq) and
98 dichloromethane (12 mL). The reaction was carried out at room temperature for 12
99 hours. The byproduct dicyclohexylurea (DCU) was removed by filtration and
100 precipitate was washed three times with ethyl acetate. The filtrate was concentrated and
101 the residue was purified by dry flash chromatography (SiO₂; eluent:
102 dichloromethane/toluene /ethyl acetate = 60:40:3), to afford 893 mg (76 %) of benzyl
103 ester **5**, as a white crystals (mp 121-123 °C) (Pénisson and Zahn, 1970). ¹H NMR (400
104 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_H 8.16 – 8.07 (m, 8H), 7.46 – 7.34 (m, 5H), 5.38 (s, 2H), 4.70 (s, 4H),
105 3.94 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ_C 166.3, 165.7, 165.7, 135.8, 134.3, 133.7,
106 133.6, 129.9, 129.8, 129.7, 128.8, 128.6, 128.4, 67.3, 63.14, 63.12, 52.6. IR (ATR) ν_{max}:
107 2963, 1717, 1581, 1505, 1454, 1437, 1412, 1344, 1275, 1131, 1106, 1022, 975, 728.
108 HRMS (ESI): m/z [M+Na]⁺ calculated for C₂₆H₂₂O₈: 485.1207; found: 485.1206.

109 **4-((2-((4-(methoxycarbonyl)benzoyl)oxy)ethoxy)carbonyl)benzoic acid (6):** The
110 catalytic amount of 10% palladium on charcoal was added into the solution of benzyl
111 ester **5** (665.2 mg; 1.44 mmol) in 1,4- dioxane (14 mL). The hydrogenolysis of
112 protected oligomer was performed under hydrogen atmosphere, with rubber balloon
113 filled with hydrogen, at room temperature for 6 h. The reaction mixture was filtered
114 through a plug of celite, solvent was removed in *vacuo*, to afford 492 mg (92 %) of
115 **PET[C/D]-COOH**, as a white crystals (mp 192-194 °C) (Pénisson and Zahn, 1970).
116 ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ_H 8.07 and 8.04 (two overlapping singlets in ratio
117 4:4, 8H), 4.66 (s, 4H), 3.87 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO- d₆): δ_C 166.7, 165.6,
118 165.2, 165.1, 135.4, 133.8, 133.5, 133.0, 129.7, 129.68, 129.65, 129.5, 63.3, 63.2, 52.7.
119 IR (ATR) ν_{max}: 2964, 2906, 2670, 2544, 1719, 1688, 1579, 1507, 1431, 1410, 1340,
120 1273, 1130, 1020, 727. HRMS (ESI): m/z [M+Na]⁺ calculated for C₁₉H₁₆O₈: 395.0737;
121 found: 395.0732.

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126

127 **Figure S2.** $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum (400 MHz) of **PET[B]-COOH** recorded in CDCl_3 and128 $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectrum (101 MHz) of **PET[B]-COOH** recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S3. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum (400 MHz) of **5** recorded in CDCl_3 and $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectrum (101 MHz) of **5** recorded in CDCl_3 .

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135 **Figure S4.** $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum (400 MHz) of **6** recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ and $^{13}\text{C NMR}$
 136 spectrum (101 MHz) of **6** recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$.

139 **Figure S5.** ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz) of mUPET1 (A) recorded in CDCl₃ and ¹³C
 140 NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of mUPET1 (A) recorded in CDCl₃.

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143 **Figure S6.** ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz) of mUPET2 (B) recorded in CDCl₃ and ¹³C
 144 NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of mUPET2 (B) recorded in CDCl₃.

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147 **Figure S7.** ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz) of mUPET3 (C) recorded in CDCl₃ and ¹³C
 148 NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of mUPET3 (C) recorded in CDCl₃.

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151 **Figure S8.** ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz) of *p*-NPhPET3 (D) recorded in CDCl₃ and

152 ¹³C NMR spectrum (101 MHz) of *p*-NPhPET3 (D) recorded in CDCl₃.

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156 **Figure S9.** Qualitative assay using 100 μ M of mUPET2 as a substrate. The reactions
157 were conducted in a total volume of 100 μ L, using 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.

158 After the addition of 10 μ L of each enzyme, the plate was left to incubate for 30
159 seconds at room temperature before being exposed to UV light.